

Social Work Intervention on the Problem of Governance in Implementation of POCSO Act, 2012 in Raipur District, Chhattisgarh

*¹Raghunath Bhardwaj & ²Dr Deena Nath Yadav**

¹Research Scholar, Department of Social Work, MATS University, Raipur, India

²Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Social Work, MATS University, Raipur, India

E-Mail: drdeenanathy@matsuniversity.ac.in

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1. Introduction

India is home to 19 percent of the world's children who are below 18 years of age. At the same time, more than one-third of the total population of the country, about 37 percent of the population, is of children below 18 years of age. But the biggest question is whether there is any special policy-planning or law against increasing violence, exploitation, abuse, sexual abuse and other criminal incidents among children? Are all the bodies and common people unanimous for the dignity, freedom, rights and protection of children? In this order, Children Home and Adoption Home, Children Home, Child Welfare Committee (CWC), District Child Protection Unit (DCPU), Special Juvenile Police Unit (SJPU), Special Juvenile Board (JJB), National and Responsibilities have been given to the State Child Rights Protection Commission (NCPCR & SCPCR), POCSO Courts and other specific structural bodies. It was only after the operationalization of the POCSO Act that emphasis was laid on compulsorily mentioning the sections of the POCSO Act along with the section of the Indian Penal Code (IPC) against the incident of sexual abuse, thereby reducing the incidence of sexual offenses against children. With child-friendly action, the culprit can be given the harshest punishment. This structural background may appear to be typical but the ground reality tells something else. Today, many policy planning and bodies have been established for child rights and protection, which provide protection against continuous sexual assault and criminal incidents related to children. But the form of its reality depends on the application and awareness of the beneficiary child and his guardian. For the significance of these values, the research presented underlines the practical aspects of the subject like intervention on the problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act 2012.

Protection of Children from Sexual Offenses Act, 2012: POCSO Act, 2012 is effective in the country (except Jammu and Kashmir) from 14 November 2012. This Act is colloquially called POCSO Act, whose full name is Protection from Sexual Offenses. The Protection of Children from Sexual Offenses Act, 2012. This law attaches importance to strict enforcement of legal provisions for the protection of children against all forms of sexual assault, harassment and all other sexual exploitation. Under this law, any person who is below 18 years of age is considered a child. That means any boy or girl below 18 years of age. This Act includes sexual assault on children, aggravated sexual assault, penetrative sexual assault, aggravated penetrative sexual assault, sexual harassment, use of a child for obscene purposes, involving or getting children involved in making and storing obscene material, abetment of crime, Committing or causing sexual assault or being directly or indirectly involved in a conspiracy is a serious act under child sexual offences. Also, the process of reporting such cases and taking statements, court process, compensation and amended Act have been described in detail. In this research, the activities related to the implementation of the Protection of Children from Sexual Offenses Act, 2012 and the challenges for their operation have been mentioned in detail. Therefore, through research, an attempt has been made to provide a new perspective in creating new knowledge through a comprehensive understanding of child sexual crimes along with their operational and diagnostic activities.

Research Methodology:

The main objective of this research is to identify the problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act and to diagnose the problems with the help of social work intervention. The nature of the presented research study is quantitative and the research is in descriptive and diagnostic design. The convenience sampling method has been used in the research under non-probability sampling. In this, the facts have been compiled by structured interview schedule by selecting 63 units from the total stakeholders (related administrative officers).

Important Fact and Data Analysis- Here the problems faced by various stakeholders in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012 are depicted. Under this, the problems faced by various stakeholders in the implementation of POCSO Act and the practical purpose of their departmental working style have been studied. All stakeholders involved in the process of implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012 in this study are Child Welfare Officer of Police Department, Child Welfare Committee (CWC), District Child Protection Unit (DCPU), Juvenile

Justice Board (JJB member), Women and Child Development Officer (WCDO), Medical Officer and the practical problems of the members of the Village Child Protection Committee have been assessed. In this regard, primary data of important aspects related to department-wise implementation related problems of all the stakeholders have been included.

Table 1: Problems faced by the Stakeholders in the implementation of The POCSO Act (2012)

SN	Stakeholders	Medium	High	Lot of high
1	Child welfare officer (SJPU)	21.9 %	78.1 %	-
2	Child welfare Committee (CWC)	50 %	50%	-
3	District Child Protection Unite (DCPU),	-	100 %	-
4	Juvenile Justice Board (JJB Members)	-	100 %	-
5	Woman and Child Development Officer (WCDO)	-	-	100 %
6	Medical Officer	-	100 %	-
7	Village Child Protection Committee	-	-	100 %

Problems of the Stakeholders in the Implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012:

1.1 More than three-fourth of the police administration (78.1%) reported more problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012. In this sequence, basic facilities like women police officers, special police units and rooms for them, adequate training and 24-hour availability of related personnel are not available in the department.

1.2 Half of the 50.0 per cent CWC stakeholders reported a high level of problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012. Mainly lack of CWC office and room for taking statement, basic facilities like compensation facility and rehabilitation are not available.

1.3 100% DCPU stakeholders have informed that the level of problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012 is high. Mainly lack of coordination and cooperation with the committee and administration formed at the block and village level, lack of girl-child home, financial management and technical resources, as well as basic facilities like compensation facility and rehabilitation are not available.

1.4 100% JJB stakeholders told that there are many problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012. Due to this reason apart from lack of public awareness about Juvenile Court, many challenges have to be faced for necessary facilities like non-availability of compensation amount.

1.5 100% WCDO Beneficiary said that there are many problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012 due to lack of staff, lack of coordination between officers and employees, lack of financial management, management of subject experts, organizing workshops and seminars. Essential features are missing.

1.6 100% Medical Officer Stakeholders stated that there is more in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012. Due to this, many challenges have to be faced for basic medical facilities like lack of skilled and well-trained medical officers, forensic kits, adapted lights, chemical tests and special rooms for them.

1.7 100% VCPC Stakeholders pointed out that there are many problems in the implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012. There has not been any kind of training and awareness, nor do they get a booklet regarding the law or any specific information related to it, as well as there is no coordination between the officers and the general public.

Conclusion:

While conducting I would like say that all these aspects make it clear that there is a negative result for the implementing side. This is a question mark on administrative action. Therefore, for child-friendly action of the administration, it is necessary that importance should be given to practical implementation on all the above aspects.

Intervention:

It is clear from the presented research results that relative to the practical purpose of the POCSO Act, 2012, the theoretical background is vast, due to which there is a huge gap between the two aspects. In this sequence, the status of implementation of the POCSO Act, 2012 is worrying, due to which the stakeholders have to face many problems in the process, so the role of social work intervention is very relevant to solve these key points. It gives importance to awareness, effective implementation and community-based problem solving at individual level, group and community level. Along with this, through social work research, social action and social welfare administration, amendments at the policy planning level, the process of making new laws, its better action and management arrangements are adjusted on priority. Therefore, according to the methodology of social work, the process of intervention is as follows which is effective for professional social worker and NGO.

1.1 Modal of Intervention by Social Case Work:

Through this technique, the psychosocial problems of a victim and her affected members are solved. In this sequence, in the difficulties faced by the children suffering from sexual abuse or their close members through guidance and counseling, hypnosis and counseling for psychosocial problems, legal guidance and counseling, intervention in the form of consultant in the process for action is done. So that the psychosocial problems faced by them, lack of awareness of POCSO Act, processing problems, difficulties in getting compensation and justice and other personal problems can be solved, for this the role of individual social worker becomes important. In this sequence, child victims of child sexual abuse, counseling for close members and relatives, awareness of law for child rights and protection, administrative departments for prevention of incidents, apart from major organizations like HAQ Delhi, Arpan NGO, CRY (CHILD Rights and You) Organizations effectively conduct social and personal work initiatives.

Model 1.1: Model for Intervention by Case social work

1.2 Modal of Intervention by Social Group

Two types of actions are taken through this method. First, a special group formed earlier is made active for child friendly policy planning and implementation. In this sequence, as coordinators, communicators and advisors prepare the already existing groups for an active role by making them aware about all aspects of the law for child sexual abuse and prevention. On the other hand, importance is given to new creative initiatives for the rights and protection of children by forming Child Protection Committees at the local and school level of the victim children, their family and close members, normal children and parents etc. Due to which the problem of child sexual abuse can be solved through group-based planning by forming a local child protection committee by the victim child, their family and close members, normal children and parents. Thus, in both the processes, by planning a child-friendly policy on a particular group against child sexual abuse, intervention is made by social workers in the form of coordinators, counseling, legal guidance as well as pressure groups and advisors in the process for action.

Model 1.2: Model for Intervention through Social Group Work

Taking social work research one step further, it presents the intervention model to diagnose a particular problem. Under this, effective planning is done through research on incidents of sexual crimes against children in different areas of the society. For this, after conducting a specific study by social work research about the causes of child sexual offenses, administrative action, implementation of POCSO Act in various departments, attitude of common people, problems in implementation etc. The model is presented which is an effective method for problem solving.

Model 1.3: Model for Intervention by Social Work Research

Under this, a systematic action will have to be taken for social change by coming together unanimously against the increasing sexual crimes against children in the society. So that the aspects of child protection should be given priority in the general public towards increasing sexual crimes with children and by uniting themselves, we can strengthen the role of mass movement for change in policy planning and implementation inconsistencies, so that necessary facilities for the protection of children are provided. and procedures can be followed.

Model 1.4: Model for Intervention by Social Action

amount received under the POCSO Act was told and the POCSO Act and its proceedings were discussed in detail and made aware.

2.2 Intervention by the researcher under group social work:

Participated in a workshop program as an expert on the issue of Protection of Children and POCSO Act, 2012 at Government Higher Secondary Girls School, Sunderkera under Abhanpur Tehsil under District Raipur. Through this programme, children were informed about safe and unsafe touch and protective procedures to avoid sexual offences. Along with this, about the ill-treatment (sexual abuse, child labor, smuggling, alcoholism etc.) of the laborers living in Kabir Nagar slum area of Raipur and the migrant families and their children and the measures for prevention. Organized an awareness program discussing about Along with this, with the help of Child Protection Unit District Raipur and Anganwadi workers, the booklet related to law was also distributed.

Disabled Public Welfare Service Committee Pamgarh District Janjgir Champa Chhattisgarh in association with Village Child Protection Committee, took special initiative in forming SHG and Disabled Children's Committee, along with rights and protection of children among these groups as well as POCSO Act, Various programs were done to create awareness about 2012.

2.3 Interventions under Social Work Research

Under this, research work was done on two important topics. In which first research about the laws and plans against violence, abuse, exploitation, injustice, misdeeds and crimes happening with children in the context of the role of changing Child Rights and Protection Acts in India and secondly for the rights of children and their protection. The research done in the context of change, rising sexual crimes against children and Indian society is a very relevant topic. Discussing several special laws and policies for the freedom, protection and promotion of children, has mentioned in detail the governmental and non-governmental efforts to curb the ever-increasing criminal incidents with children. Both the research work presented enriches the practical knowledge about child sexual crime and policy planning related to its prevention through social work research.

2.4 Interventions under Social Action

In order to sensitize the students to the awareness of the POCSO Act, 2012 and various aspects of child sexual offenses in various disciplines related to social sciences, through a letter

to Nagpur University, the laws related to child sexual offenses and prevention have been included in the curriculum. Demanded to give importance to academic discussion through the teaching-learning process. Whose impact will be directly on community thinking. In this initiative cooperation of principals of different colleges of Wardha, Nagpur, Bhandara was taken.

Important Demands:

1. Inclusion of POCSO Act, 2012 issues in the curriculum in interdisciplinary subjects of other social sciences like social work.
2. To conduct a comprehensive course on various aspects of child protection along with child welfare.
3. Seminars should be organized on various aspects of child development and protection.
4. Importance should be given to academic discussions on various aspects of child development and protection.

In this way, after the consent of the students for all the important demands, with the approval of the principals, the action of social action for academic contribution and role on the aspects of child protection was completed.

Tips for Administrative Area:

- ❖ Appropriate resources should be made available for effective publicity in remote areas of POCSO Act, 2012 and child rights and protection related policy-planning.
- ❖ It is necessary to appoint permanent and adequate number of staff members of the District Child Protection Unit (DCPU). In this sequence, excellent initiative is being taken in the state of Bihar. By appointing Gazette Officers (Assistant Director District Child Protection Officer) in the Child Protection Unit, all the important charges like financial, are independently received by the Child Protection Unit. This process is monitored by regular meetings and documentation. There, by setting up a shelter home for children, women, the elderly and the disabled at one place, effective planning should be implemented at the grassroots level.
- ❖ Members of the District Child Protection Unit (DCPU) should be expanded, administrative officers and employees should be appointed at the block and village level.
- ❖ Integrated Child Protection Scheme (ICPS) should be given independent charge at Directorate level, so that all policy planning related to child protection can be implemented by independent charge.

- ❖ Child safety related facilities like school transport, protection against sexual exploitation, child rights should be given importance.
- ❖ Adequate financial management and availability of resources should be given special importance in the Integrated Child Protection Scheme (ICPS).
- ❖ For better implementation of policy-planning related to child rights and protection, importance should be given to the monitoring work by District Planning Committee and Child Protection Committee.
- ❖ Emphasis on making booklets, video clips for disseminating policy-planning related to child rights and protection, especially adoption policy, POCSO Act and Child Labor Act, preventing child marriage in regional language Chhattisgarhi, Halbi, Gondi language Needed
- ❖ To give immediate relief to the victims of child sexual crimes, compensation amount should be given, protection should be given to the victim and the family, as well as establishment of special advisory committees and organizations should be done compulsorily at government and non-government level.
- ❖ The victim of child sexual crime should be given reservation on special occasions for a better life. So that the social, cultural and economic security of the victim child can be ensured.
- ❖ There is a need to allocate more budget than average in the field of child protection. So that proper resources can be made available. Because so far the lowest budget allocation has been made in the child protection sector. Therefore, there is a need for adequate financial allocation for basic changes in the field of child protection with special monitoring.

References:

- 2016). *बच्चों की देखरेख एवं संरक्षण*. रायपुर : महिला एवं बाल विकास विभाग ..
- (2016). *Annual reports 2015-16*. Raipur:CGSCPCR.
- (2016). *Crime in India*. NCRB, Ministry of Home Affairs. Delhi: National Crime Record Buero.
- (2016). *National Crime record Beuro*. Nai Delhi: Ministry of home affairs.

- Aiken, M. Moran, M. Berry, M.J. (2011). *Child Abuse Material and Internet Cyber psychology of online child related sex offending*. Interpol specialist group (pp. 1-22). Lyons: Interpol specialist group.
- Ali, Bhatri. Adenwalla, Maharukh. Pinnekar, Sangeeta. (2017). *Implementation of The POCSO Act tools. Gap & Challenge*. Delhi: HAQ.
- Arpan : Towards Freedom from Child Sexual Abuse. (2017). *annual report*. Mumbai: Arpan: Towards Freedom from Child Sexual Abuse.
- Babel, D. B. (2014). *The Protection of children from Sexual Offence Act, 2012*. Raipur : India Publishing Company.
- Bharti Alli, Inshi Ganugali, Tukral. (2018). *बाल व्यापार के विरुद्ध संघर्ष: एक प्रशिक्षण पुस्तिका*.
- Chawla, P. (2018, 10 20). <https://www.gkexams.com/ask/34676-Bal-Vivah-Ka-Itihas>. Retrieved 12 26, 2020, from <https://www.gkexams.com/>: <https://www.gkexams.com/>
- Enakshi Ganguly Thukra, Farhana Yasmin, Kumar Shailabh. (2015). *Budget for Children in India 2008-09 to 2013-14*. HAQ: Center for Child Rights. Delhi: HAQ: Center for Child Rights.
- Ganguli, I. (2019). *Parliament Watch! Children's Issues in Parliament 2018-19*. HAQ, Parliament Debet. Delhi: HAQ.